

PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL AND LEGAL CONSEQUENCES OF DRUNK DRIVING

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Annotation. This article describes the concept, types and methods of detecting offenses for drunk driving, the procedure for documentation, in connection with this, proposals and recommendations are developed to improve the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan on administrative responsibility.

Key words: traffic, vehicle, offense, medical examination, drunk driver.

ПСИХОФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАВОВЫЕ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ ВОЖДЕНИЯ ТРАНСПОРТНЫХ СРЕДСТВ В НЕТРЕЗВОМ ВИДЕ

Аннотация. В статье описываются понятие, виды и методы выявления правонарушений за вождение в нетрезвом виде, порядок документирования, в связи с этим разработаны предложения и рекомендации по совершенствованию законодательства Республики Узбекистан об административной ответственности.

Ключевые слова: дорожное движение, транспортное средство, правонарушение, медицинский осмотр, нетрезвое состояние водителя.

One of the characteristics of alcohol is that even with its small doses, the reliability of the driver's activity decreases sharply, that is, the functions of the cerebral hemispheres do not work normally, the state of excitement, and the ability to control oneself and behavior appear. Intoxication and intoxication are different. Of course, the effect of taking alcohol can last for several hours (2-3 days). In a state of paralysis, the driver's sensorimotor response experiences a period of braking. In this case, violations of traffic safety rules are observed.

According to experts, even at the lowest level of drunkenness, traffic safety and road traffic accidents increase 7 times. Alcohol consumption slows down the

recovery of driving ability. In studies, 70% of drivers who drank alcohol did not get rid of fatigue after a night's sleep. And the drivers did not feel rested. On the contrary, it is noted that he woke up with fatigue. Observations have shown that up to 500,000 cars are involved in city street traffic every day, among which there are definitely drunk drivers. At the same time, properly organized control turns out to be very effective, and with the efforts of the internal organs, drunk drivers are caught and punished.

Alcoholic beverages, like drugs, affect the central nervous system, primarily the cerebral cortex. Such substances inhibit the cortex of the brain and increase the state of excitement. Under the influence of alcohol, the driver loses self-control, does not feel responsible for what is happening around him. Concentration and distribution of attention is disturbed. The listed psychophysiological disorders prepare the ground for the driver to make mistakes such as speeding up, rushing, changing direction, overtaking. As a result of research, drivers in such situations increase "perseverance", "courage". As a result of alcohol consumption, there is also a disturbance in thinking. Also, visual acuity, color separation, coordination disorders, muscle sensitivity and strength also decrease. In addition to these, the behavior of a drunk or drowsy driver is characterized by irritability, emotional instability, impaired concentration, sleep disorders, and fatigue.

It is also very important to know the time when alcohol drinks affect the driver's body. It is known that these drinks are absorbed into the body 20-30 minutes after consumption. The state of intoxication is observed in 1-1.5 hours. The first signs of intoxication appear after drinking 0.5 mg per 1 kg of body weight. That's 30g for a 60kg person. gives the conclusion that the alcoholic drink is enough to intoxicate him.

Today, as a result of the reforms carried out in the judicial system, it is possible to timely identify and take appropriate measures by law enforcement officers. This is of great importance in ensuring the safety and health of our citizens, and in compensating material and moral damages. We all know very well that if appropriate measures are not taken to prevent the violation in time, or if the detected violations are not dealt with according to our legislation, such violations may pose a serious threat to our society, the lives and health of our citizens in the future. Among the ongoing reforms, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-27 of November 29, 2021 "On approval of the concept of public security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and measures for its implementation" and January 28, 2022 "New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 In order to ensure the implementation of the decree No. PF-60 "on development strategy", as well as to further improve the system of traffic organization, develop the infrastructure of highways and create favorable conditions for road users, the following are the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of

Uzbekistan and its regional divisions was defined as an important task:

firstly, to establish a qualitatively new procedure for the organization of the activities of the republican, middle and lower divisions of traffic safety, in which their main tasks and functions, as well as the personal responsibility of leaders and employees for the performance of the tasks assigned to them, will be clearly defined and distributed;

secondly, on the basis of a systematic comprehensive analysis and elimination of the causes and conditions that allow the occurrence of traffic accidents and congestion on the roads, especially in the city of Tashkent, prevention of traffic violations, traffic accidents and improving the road congestion prevention system;

thirdly, further expansion of automated traffic regulation, video surveillance and traffic violation recording systems, and other technical means, which ensure the high efficiency of control, timely detection of violations and putting an end to them, first of all, in regional centers;

fourth, to ensure unconditional compliance with the established requirements for maintaining roads and equipping them with road signs, information signs, and other technical means of traffic regulation;

fifth, to develop a system of effective explanatory work aimed at increasing the culture of road traffic participants' compliance with traffic rules among citizens, including by expanding and improving the forms and methods of propaganda work among the population;

sixth, to ensure unconditional observance of the rights of road users, respect for their honor and dignity, and strict adherence to the rules of behavior and etiquette during service.

Currently, many works have been carried out and are being continued in connection with the implementation of these important tasks. Among them are modern roads to prevent traffic jams, public transport facilities for the population. Along with the construction of modern highways being built in our country, ensuring the safety of road users moving on these roads is one of the most important tasks. In order to ensure the safety of traffic on the roads, as a result of the implementation of many amendments and additions to our existing laws, a sharp decrease in offenses involving vehicles is being achieved. In addition to the reduction of offenses committed with the participation of vehicles, in some cases these offenses cause serious damage to the lives and health of innocent people. The difference between the offense of driving under the influence of vehicles and offenses related to other means of transport is that this offense has a high risk of serious consequences.

Inspection to determine whether drivers of vehicles are intoxicated due to the influence of alcoholic beverages It is carried out with the help of a special technical tool - a breathalyzer, the results of which are reflected on paper. The medical

examination to determine whether the drivers of vehicles are under the influence of alcoholic beverages, drugs or in a special way is carried out by the responsible staff of the district and city treatment-preventive institutions directly with the participation of the employees of State Road Safety Service. should be conducted, if the examination is carried out in a different way, the given conclusion may be invalidated. The basis for an investigation to determine whether he is under the influence of alcohol or in a special way is:

- smell of alcohol coming from the mouth of the driver;
- driver's inability to stand in one position (wobble);
- the driver's speech is impaired;
- trembling of the driver's hands;
- a significant change in the color of the driver's face.

According to Article 292 of the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan, if there are sufficient grounds to believe that the driver of the vehicle is in a state of intoxication, he must be removed from driving the vehicle and undergo an examination in the prescribed manner to determine the state of intoxication. This article stipulates that this person will be sent for examination and this examination will be carried out in the order established by the Ministry of Internal Affairs, Ministry of Health and Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Medical examination of vehicle drivers to determine whether they are under the influence of alcoholic beverages, drugs or in a special way is carried out on the basis of their identity documents.

Making a medical conclusion that a person is under the influence of alcoholic beverages, narcotic drugs or in a special way is based on the results of a blood laboratory test.

A medical conclusion that a person has consumed an alcohol product is issued in cases where the concentration of an alcohol product in the blood is 0.3 ppm or more, if the concentration in the blood is less than 0.3 ppm, a conclusion that a person has consumed an alcohol product is not issued. If there is appropriate laboratory equipment in the treatment-prophylactic institutions where biological fluids were taken, the examination of these fluids is carried out in these institutions or sent for examination to the chemical-toxicological laboratories under the regional bureaus of forensic medical expertise. The collection and delivery of samples of biological fluids is carried out in accordance with the procedure established by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The report of the results of chemical examination by forensic medical examination bureaus must be issued no later than seven days after the delivery of biological fluids. In order to determine the quantity and quality of alcohol contained in exhaled breath, alcoholic beverages contained in human biological fluids, the quantity and quality of other means that caused intoxication due

to the influence of narcotic drugs or in a special way, the technical means allowed for use in the Republic of Uzbekistan and passed the inspection are used.

When a person is taken to a medical examination, a report on the results of the examination is drawn up in two copies. In the protocol, the date of the examination and the order number are indicated in accordance with the order number of the record book of persons who have passed the medical examination to determine whether they are under the influence of alcoholic beverages, narcotic drugs or in a special way. All clauses of the protocol are completed without any reduction or other changes. The protocol is signed by the doctor who conducted the medical examination and confirmed with the seal of the medical institution where the examination was conducted. Treatment-prophylactic institutions must have examination report forms. In the absence of examination report forms in treatment-prophylactic institutions, a free-form report is drawn up reflecting all the information indicated in them. Upon his request, a person who has undergone a medical examination must be given a copy of the medical examination report and the information about the medical examination must be recorded in a specially sewn, numbered notebook with the signature of the head of the medical institution and the seal of the organization. The basis of the conclusion about the condition of the examined person is the results of a complex medical examination, which takes into account the results of the laboratory examination of the composition of biological fluids and exhaled air. In cases where the examined person refuses the examination or some type of examination, the doctor will write "refused examination" in the notebook and report. A conclusion is made on the basis of a medical examination, in which the condition of the examined person at the time of the examination should be clearly explained. When making a conclusion, the doctor must determine one of the following situations:

- state of intoxication was not detected;
- the state of alcohol intoxication was determined;
- the state of intoxication due to the influence of drugs or in a special way was determined;
- there are disorders of the functional state that require exclusion from work with a high risk source in terms of health status.

The conclusion on the results of the medical examination will be presented to the examined person in front of the State Road Safety Service employee who brought it. In cases where the examinee has objections to the conclusion, he has the right to demand re-examination at another medical institution. In this case, the re-medical examination should be carried out in the presence of an employee of the National Health Service at another nearby medical institution within two hours from the time when the symptoms of intoxication were detected or the traffic accident occurred. In cases where there is a need to conduct a medical examination of persons who have

the right to immunity in the jurisdiction of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the examination is carried out only with their consent according to general principles.

In conclusion, we would like to emphasize that it is important to strengthen the measures to prevent the offense of driving a vehicle while intoxicated, to study international experiences in this regard, and to introduce the use of modern technologies for accurate and short-term detection of the offense. No one can guarantee that as a result of driving a vehicle under the influence of alcohol, every person, driver will not become the cause of serious consequences.

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